

AI-PRISM

D2.1 – Reference Framework and Specifications and Specifications (I)

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Acronyms and definitions

Acronym	Meaning
AD	Ambient Digitalization
AGV	Automated Guided Vehicles
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AMR	Autonomous Mobile Robot
CD	Continuous Deployment
CDE	Continuous Delivery
CI	Continuous Integration
CM	Communication Modules
DDS	Data Distribution Service
DOA	Description of the Action
DR	Agent Level Reasoning Modules
DS	Data Platforms
eTaSL	A task specification language
HI	Human Machine Interaction Modules
HMI	Human Machine Interaction
HW	Hardware
IIoT	Industrial Internet of Things
IoT	Internet of Things
IT	Information Technology
MAC	Medium Access Control
NFV	Network Function Virtualization

OT	Operational Technology
PD	Programming with Demonstration
PE	Perception Enhancing
QDSN	Quick Deployment Sensor Network
QoS	Quality of Service
RA	Reference Architecture
RGB	Red Green Blue
ROS	Robot Operating System
SDN	Software Defined Networks
SE	Simulation Environment
SP	Human Safety Management Procedures
SSH	Social Sciences Humanities
TSN	Time Sensitive Networks
WSN	Wireless Sensor Networks

Executive summary

This deliverable describes the AI-PRISM reference architecture, which is an abstract, high-level description of the reference architecture of AI-PRISM. It also contains a high-level description of the different components of AI-PRISM, drafted in M3, and completed until M12. The objective is to build a common understanding of ‘what is AI-PRISM?’ that extends the definitions included in the DOA and that provides a common framework to further develop the answers to the questions: ‘how is AI-PRISM used?’ (answered in T2.2 – Usage Models and Mockups), ‘how does AI-PRISM work?’ (answered in T2.3 – Functional Specification), and ‘how is AI-PRISM implemented?’ (answered in T2.4 – Technical Specification).

The AI-PRISM project

AI-PRISM will provide industrial users with human-centred artificial intelligence (AI)-based solutions to create a more efficient, resilient, digital, sustainable, and high-quality European manufacturing industry.

To do so, we will develop an integrated and scalable environment with solutions adapted to dynamic and unpredictable manufacturing scenarios that require tasks that are difficult to automate and where speed and versatility are essential to meet users' needs. Furthermore, the solutions will be specific to semi-automated and collaborative manufacturing in flexible production processes and will not require specific robotic programming skills.

Our solutions ecosystem will have four main pillars:

1. A human-centred collaborative robotic platform oriented to ease hard-to-automate manufacturing tasks.
2. A human-robot cooperative environment powered by trustworthy AI.
3. Social human-agent-robots teams' collaboration — AI-based safety monitoring and robot control mechanisms to detect and avoid unsafe situations and ensure social and physical safety.
4. An open-access network portal to offer compliant infrastructure.

To evaluate our solutions' performance, transferability, scalability, and large-scale deployment, we will perform demonstrations in real operating environments. Specifically, in four user pilots involving key manufacturing sectors — furniture, food/beverage, built-in appliances, and electronics —, types of robots and industrial processes that are difficult to automate, plus a generic demonstration facility.

In addition to seeking quantitative improvements in the manufacturing sector, AI-PRISM aims to use technological innovation to support a paradigm shift in which AI, robotics and Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) are integrated into the manufacturing domain for the improvement of flexible production processes, becoming a viable and widespread alternative for European factories.

During the next three years, 25 partners from 12 countries will join forces to make AI-PRISM a reality. From educational institutions to research and technology organisations, robot manufacturers, industries and use case providers; our interdisciplinary consortium brings together all the actors of the human-robot collaboration value chain and involves key experts in SSH, standardisation, exploitation, and dissemination.

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1. Introduction

1.1. Objectives and Methodology

The first objective of this task is to deliver a reference architecture that frames the key technical results of AI-PRISM. The AI-PRISM Reference Architecture (RA) defines the technical structure and establishes the relations between the key technical results identified in the DOA. This way, the AI-PRISM RA will provide a template solution for the technical implementation of AI-PRISM, through the integration of the envisioned key technical results. In this sense, the DOA includes different types of technical results:

1. **Hardware components.** Hardware equipment required to deploy an AI-PRISM collaboration ambient.
2. **Communication networks.** Communication network equipment enabling real time communications in the collaboration ambient.
3. **Runtime Environments.** Components providing the execution environment for software components.
4. **Software components.** Components implementing the functions and behaviours of AI-PRISM.

First, the AI-PRISM RA establishes the relationships between hardware components, communication networks, runtime environments, and software components. Then, based on these relationships, this document describes the main characteristics, the candidate solutions that can be integrated and re-used, and the baseline specifications, defined as the minimum configuration necessary to instantiate an AI-PRISM collaboration ambient. Then, for each of the software components, this document provides a description, a list of functional components mapped to the AI-PRISM RA, and an indication of the expected input and output interfaces. Also, the main interactions between components will be identified, as well as interactions with functions outside the scope of AI-PRISM.

Delivering a low-level, detailed description of the interactions, procedures, or specifications of AI-PRISM technical results is out of the scope of this deliverable. Instead, the objective is to provide an abstract description of the technical architecture of AI-PRISM to identify the main equipment and communication networks involved, and how the different AI-PRISM components interact between them within this technical infrastructure. The adoption of this reference architecture will ensure the applicability and consistency of the key technical results of AI-PRISM. Another objective of this deliverable is to improve the interoperability of the different components, by establishing common mechanisms for the implementation of communication interfaces and by aligning the reference architecture with standards and industry best practices. Furthermore, the adoption of the reference architecture will help identifying synergies and development assets common to several components. Later, during the implementation phase, AI-PRISM can provide a unified response to these common

Table 1: Technical Results

Technical Result	Description
AI-PRISM Human Centred Collaborative Robotic Platform	
AI-PRISM ROS Framework	Robot Operating System (ROS) Framework to manage the deployment of ROS modules. Core ROS (2) packages which together with a development guideline library will provide a technological common ground for the integration of the (AI-PRISM) functional modules.
AI-PRISM Base Hardware	Supported base hardware interfaces (for Automated Guided Vehicles (AGVs), mobile robots, industrial robots, etc). Dedicated drivers for supported Hardware (HW) modules for human/robot collaboration.
AI-PRISM Communications Modules	ROS packages that will enable real-time communication within the AI-PRISM Data Platform and with other devices.
AI-PRISM Ambient sensing infrastructure	Supported sensors and cameras to sense the environment. RGB and depth sensors will be employed to digitalize the working environment and the components acting in it, such as robotic agents, human workers, obstacles, and tools. The data acquired in the form of 2D visual content and 3D geometrical content will be fused to create textured 3D point clouds capturing the environment at a precise time frame. The scene reconstruction will be dynamically updated to account for dynamic agents moving in the environment. Additional sensors, such as thermal or infrared cameras, will be employed to consider complementary information. Algorithms to automatically calibrate such sensors will be provided.
AI-PRISM Real Time Communications Network	Supported real-time communication hardware. Software Defined Networks (SDN), Quick Deployment Sensor Network (QDSN), and Wireless Sensor Networks (WSN) sensor network control and management. The distributed nature of the AI-PRISM components (cobots, AGVs, sensors, people, tools) will require a high-performance communication network to ensure their reliable and real-time operation and integration. The industry relies on classic technologies and architectures that are not flexible enough to enable these new Industry 4.0 needs, where wireless technologies and mobility requirements are more present day by day. This technological layer enables a robust, real-time and secure integration between all the AI-PRISM components, but with the challenge of providing also the needed flexibility, mobility and scalability. State-of-the-art technologies based on deterministic ethernet, Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT), flexible wireless sensing layers and the integration of SDN in the industry, will be the main drivers.
AI-PRISM IIoT Platform	Edge/Cloud platform to support the deployment of data services, simulation services and ROS Framework.
AI-PRISM Data Platform	Data services to support AI-based solutions. It comprises the AI-PRISM Data Model, the Data Broker, the Repositories, and the Data Management functions.
AI-PRISM Simulation Environment	Software services to run Simulation models representing the collaboration ambient, including robots, industrial equipment, and human agents.
AI-PRISM Ambient Digitalisation Modules	Comprehends software modules to integrate data acquired with the AI-PRISM Ambient sensing infrastructure. The data acquired in the form of 2D visual content and 3D geometrical content will be fused to create textured 3D point clouds capturing the environment at a precise time frame. The scene reconstruction will be dynamically updated to account for dynamic agents moving in the environment.
AI-PRISM Human Robot Cooperation Ambient	
AI-PRISM CI/CD Framework for AI-based Solutions	Pipelines and infrastructure to support AI-based development, integration and validation. The tooling and infrastructure required to manage AI-based solutions along their lifecycle, considering design, development, discovery, deployment, training, validation, use, monitoring, and improvement.

AI-PRISM AI-based Perception Enhancing Modules	AI-based modules to enhance perception capabilities. Deep learning models will be developed to process the spatio-temporal reconstruction of the environment to produce high-level features capable to describe workers' actions during their working tasks in order to understand their activities and monitor their health status. The activity understanding will be used to teach robot agents how to mimic human activities and safely collaborate with them in the workplace. The health status monitoring will be used to judge how best to assist in, or replace, current parts of a worker's activity, thus improving their conditions. Multi-modal models will be explored to fully account for the different sensor modalities. Recurrent neural networks will be explored to account for the temporal aspect of our input data.
AI-PRISM AI-based Agent Level Reasoning Enhancing Modules	An AI-based module that handles the discrete level reasoning/planning between a single robot system and a user interacting with the system. This system will closely interact with the low-level constraint-based controller and will need to exploit the information from AI-based ambient-level reasoning modules in T4.4.
AI-PRISM AI-based Ambient Level Reasoning Enhancing Modules	AI-based modules to enhance the collaboration of agents in the ambient. It includes models and algorithms to solve problems related to the coordination of humans and robotic agents in the ambient, like task allocation, or optimal routing. It also includes modules to enable the control of operations at the ambient level, monitoring events in the ambient and acting in response (e.g. re-allocating tasks or changing the routing) to ensure performance.
AI-PRISM Human - Machine Interaction (HMI) Modules	Integrate the sensor-modalities used in the project in a probabilistic motion/force model for use during execution using a constraint-based framework, both during the learning phase and during the execution phase
AI-PRISM Programming by Demonstration Environment	Integration of the constraint-based framework eTaSL (task specification language for reactive control of robot systems) in the project middleware. Development of the appropriate drivers for the robot system. Programming-by-demonstration is realized by combining model-based constraints with motion and force information from demonstrations. Task definitions will be composed that are appropriate for the classes of tasks considered in the project. This continuous-level Human Robot Interface (HRI) module will integrate with discrete events from the agent-based reasoning modules.
Social Human-Agent-Robots Teams Collaboration	
AI-PRISM Human Safety Management Procedures	The solution improves the safety in warehouses, and in general in workplaces where there are some risks of incident caused by wrong behavior in particular zones or where there are machines with risk of collision. The AI-PRISM Human Safety Management Procedures allows us to check in real-time way the situation in every part of the plant, and warn supervisors if something dangerous or non-compliant happens. The solution can be integrated with other systems/sources of information (i.e. information on parameters of use and operation of equipment such as temperature, pressure, position, etc.) that appropriately analyzed and correlated could highlight any situations of alarm/danger;
AI-PRISM Open Access Network Portal	
AI-PRISM Network Suite	Service suite composed of a dynamic web-based user interface, an online Digital Twin builder, user access control, digital certification, an interactive training engine, scheduling, and optimization engine

1.1. Glossary

This section contains some definitions that are important to understand the objectives of AI-PRISM and the scope of the different technical results.

Table 2: Glossary

Term	Definition
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AI-PRISM component	A technical result of the AI-PRISM project, corresponding to a Key Exploitable Result, identified in the DOA, and described in AI-PRISM Reference Framework.
AI-PRISM ambient	A physical space where humans and robots can collaborate in a secure way thanks to AI-PRISM components
Real time communications	An SDN-based network architecture that provides integration and interaction between different network technologies but always focuses on keeping the end-to-end quality of service.
Reactive Robot Control	The instantaneous motion of the robot is only partially defined by offline specified targets because, during the execution of the motion, the robot's target is adapted based on online sensor feedback. That reactivity holds for both the continuous and discrete aspects of the robot control.
AI-PRISM modules	An independent software component developed in AI-PRISM that is designed to provide specific functionalities in a collaboration ambient for specific use cases, and that can be discovered, selected, and installed in an AI-PRISM ambient.

2. Reference Architecture

This section provides a high-level abstract description of AI-PRISM.

2.1. Reference Architecture Overview

The AI-PRISM RA is based on standard based reference architectures and reference models. The underlying standard which defines conventions and definitions for architecting complex software systems is the ISO/IEC/IEEE 42010 standard for systems and software engineering architecture descriptions [1]. The Industrial Internet Architecture Framework (IIRA) [2] is an example of a Reference Architecture applying the ISO/IEC/IEEE Architecture Description definitions. [3] and [4] describe and align prominent reference architectures and reference models for Industry 4.0 cyber-physical systems. Software architectures are more than frameworks for execution of functions and exchange of data: the more important aspects deal with **how** components in the system have to behave and adapt their behaviour to that of other components; in this context, several architectural patterns and insights have matured during the last 50 years, of which most have not been integrated into robotic systems. [5] describes many architectural patterns - conceptualization of essential features of a system implementation in a way that is easy to understand by stakeholders - that are relevant for complex robotic systems and most notably for distributed systems, where the implicit assumption of **exactly once delivery** of data does hold in practice when combined with **low latency**.

Figure 2: AI-PRISM Reference Architecture

The overall architecture in Figure 2 depicts a high-level, simplified, and abstracted view of the AI-PRISM system, so that it provides an initial architectural reference for technical partners, which can be refined and improved upon without holding back or restraining any design consideration during the definition of the system. The AI-PRISM RA is based on the IIRA three-tier architecture pattern, which is a multi-tiered architecture pattern which comprises the edge, platform, and enterprise tiers, and three networks, the proximity network, the access network, and the service network. These concepts are adapted to the AI-PRISM vision in the AI-PRISM RA, which divides the system into 3 primary zones or tiers, namely the device tier, the fog tier, and the device tier. The following subsections provide a brief overview of each of the tiers identified in the AI-PRISM RA.

2.1.1. Edge Tier

The device tier groups all the different devices in the ambient, including sensors, robots, and other manufacturing equipment, collectively referred to as edge devices. The hardware specifications of the sensing infrastructure and the robot hardware vary depending on the specific use cases, however there is a minimum configuration and specifications common to all instances of AI-PRISM. The AI-PRISM RA device tier differentiates the devices required to sense the collaborative ambient and the humans in the ambient (**Ambient and Human Sensing Infrastructure**, described in section 3.1)

from the hardware (**AI-PRISM Base Hardware**, described in **section 3.2** and software components on-board robotic agents (**AI-PRISM ROS Framework**, described in **section 4.1**), and the industrial control systems which are integrated through the AI-PRISM Data Platform Services (**section 5.1.2**). The edge tier also differentiates the robot agents in the ambient that will use the AI-PRISM base hardware and ROS network from other robots in the collaborative ambient that may use a different hardware and/or operating system. Moreover, the AI-PRISM considers sensors, robots, and other industrial devices in a generic way. The specific characteristics of this tier will vary significantly depending on the specific use cases. Defining the specific sensors or controllers is out of the scope of the AI-PRISM RA.

2.1.2. Ambient Network

The ambient network connects the edge devices and provides real-time communication support between these edge devices and AI-PRISM software modules running in the fog tier. Edge devices will be typically connected to a bridge or gateway module, which is a software module that bridges a device or a cluster of devices to the data services in the AI-PRISM Data Platform Services layer. This bridge modules can be executed either at the edge tier (e.g. a data bridge device on board the robot that interconnects the systems on board the robot with the AI-PRISM Data Platform), or at the fog tier (e.g. a southbound communication module that collects data and sends actuation commands to edge devices using communication protocols supported by those devices). The network functions providing real-time communications capabilities are executed in the SDN / NFV (Network Functions Virtualization) Network Infrastructure, which is further described in **section 3.3**.

2.1.3. Fog Tier

The fog tier groups the AI-PRISM components that are deployed between the edge tier and the cloud tier. The fog tier components are deployed in a fog cluster which is managed by the end-user organisation (there is normally one cluster per user organisation location). The fog cluster is controlled by the cluster control function of the AI-PRISM IIoT Platform described in **section 4.2** and is divided into the following layers or sub-zones.

- 1. AI-PRISM Data Platform Services.** Service layer providing data storage and streaming services for data collected from edge devices in the ambient. The AI-PRISM Data Platform Services are described in **section 5.1.1**.
- 2. Simulation Modules.** AI-PRISM modules (see glossary or **section 3.4** for a more precise definition) to simulate the behaviour of human, robots, or equipment in the ambient.
- 3. Perception Modules.** AI-PRISM modules enhancing the perception capabilities of agents in the collaboration ambient.
- 4. Reasoning Modules.** AI-PRISM modules enhancing the reasoning capabilities of agents in the collaboration ambient.

- 5. Collaboration Modules.** AI-PRISM modules ensuring safe interactions between human and robot agents in the ambient, as well as secure remote access to enable open access to local functions.

2.1.4. Cloud Tier

The cloud tier groups the components that enable Continuous Integration and Continuous Deployment (CI/CD) of solutions (AI-PRISM CI/CD Services), and the components that enable open access to AI-PRISM equipment to external collaborators (AI-PRISM Collaboration Network Services). These components are deployed in the **cloud cluster** in separate sub-zones. Normally, there will be only an instance of the cloud cluster providing these services for all AI-PRISM use cases.

Subsequent sections of this document provide a technical description of the AI-PRISM components, including interfaces, main functions, and important procedures for the management of their lifecycle.

3. Networks and Equipment

This section provides the baseline technical specifications for the different networks and equipment components identified in the AI-PRISM RA.

3.1. AI-PRISM Ambient and Human Sensing Infrastructure

The AI-PRISM Ambient and Human Sensing Infrastructure consists of sensing equipment to sense the collaboration ambient and the equipment, agents, and other elements in the ambient (robots, humans, obstacles, tools, etc.).

WSN and sensing devices, together with the Internet of Things (IoT) paradigm, constitute the foundation of the AI-PRISM Project, since it represents the main way through which our system can sense the physical world. In this sense, the IoT is defined as a paradigm in which internet connectivity and computing capability extend to real-world objects, devices, and sensors[6]. AI-PRISM adopts this IoT paradigm, where sensors measure continuously physical events in the collaboration ambient and later, the collected data are transferred via the SDN Network Infrastructure to the AI-PRISM Data Platform Services which enable the creation of digital models of the world, and the development of enhanced perception and reasoning capabilities based on these digital models.

3.1.1. Baseline Technical Specifications

A collection of distributed and calibrated sensors will be installed in the working environment to enable two core AI-PRISM modules: (i) Ambient Digitalization (AD), which will acquire the content of the scene in digital form, and (ii) Perception Enhancing (PE), which will process the digital representation of the scene content to accomplish the task at hand.

Figure 3. Ambient Sensing Infrastructure

The collection of sensors will contain both mobile (i.e. wearable, robot mounted) and environmental (e.g. fixed onto walls, ceiling) sensors to acquire information of the workplace and the components acting in it (e.g. human workers, robotic agents, obstacles, and tools) under different view-points, reducing occlusions and clutter.

Different types of sensors will be considered to capture complementary information. In this version of the specifications, we hypothesize that Red Green Blue (RGB) and depth sensors will be used by default for all the use cases to identify agents in the workplace, whereas optional sensors like thermal or infrared sensors will be employed where needed. But in any case, and stated above, the architectural characteristics of the sensor network are use case dependent and this section includes some initial suggestions that may change in future releases of the document.

To record the whole workspace, it would be recommendable using one or several **Intel RealSense DR435 Camera**¹, which, alone, can provide stereo vision data, but the more cameras we add to the workspace, the more reliable the data becomes.

Automated sensor health and (re)calibration algorithms will be implemented to create a rich network of signals that are interrelated in the same reference system. Based on this information, the goal of the AD module is to merge the information captured by the sensors, collected from multiple view-points and different modalities, to create a 4D representation of the working environment containing its 3D reconstruction at different time frames (thus being time regarded as a 4th dimension). The 3D reconstruction will be represented as a point cloud, whose points are associated with 3D coordinates and additional meta information (e.g. RGB colour, temperature, infrared radiation) if available.

On the other hand, the goal of the PE module is to use machine learning algorithms to process the 4D representation of the environment to produce high-level features capable to solve different tasks,

¹ <https://www.intelrealsense.com/depth-camera-d457/>

including: (i) monitoring the activities of human workers and robot agents cooperating in the same environment and understanding their health status, (ii) understanding which activity is being carried out, (iii) learn the sequence of actions that compose a work task from a human worker in order to train a robot agent to mimic it, and (iv) generate alerts when predicting the presence of obstacles/people.

Both AD and PE module will be described in detail in **section 5** in future releases of this document.

3.2. AI-PRISM Base Hardware

As described in the Reference Architecture, the AI-PRISM Base Hardware is the hardware that will host the execution of the AI-PRISM software on-board the robot, not running in the fog cluster. AI-PRISM is a distributed system [7], in the sense that software modules can be executed on-board each of the robots in the ambient, and also in other tiers, primarily the fog tier, as will be further elaborated below and in **section 3.4**. Moreover, in AI-PRISM, each of the instances of the AI-PRISM base hardware in a given ambient is considered an edge device. The fog cluster will host the AI-PRISM Data Platform Services, including device management functions to manage edge devices, and the SDN / NFV Network Infrastructure provides real-time communications support between software components distributed in edge devices and the fog tier. The concepts of edge computing and fog computing are strongly interlinked and for the sake of clarity, this section provides a brief description in the context of AI-PRISM.

Edge computing extends the processing power of IoT devices, using hardware that is installed physically close and directly connected to the device [8]. Similarly, fog computing is defined as a horizontal system-level architecture that distributes computing in the close vicinity of the device, along the path to the cloud [8]. From these definitions, the AI-PRISM Base Hardware is the hardware physically installed on-board the robot, directly connected to the robot system, and the fog cluster spans the hardware components on-board the robot for edge computing, plus any additional hardware required to support the software components deployed in the fog tier (between the AI-PRISM hardware and the cloud), connected to the AI-PRISM base hardware through the SDN / NFV Network infrastructure.

Figure 4: Fog computing architecture

Figure 4 shows an example of such a fog computing architecture.

3.2.1. Baseline Technical Specifications

As with the ambient sensing technology, the specific hardware installed in the robot is very use case dependent, and there are no hard requirements, bearing in mind that the baseline technical specifications for the fog cluster are described below in **section 3.4.1**, and that the AI-PRISM specifications should be generic and compatible with different robotic solutions. In line with previous section, this section includes some baseline suggestions that may be updated in future releases.

As specified in **section 3.1** above, the system will require sensors that can provide RGB-Depth data. As such, for short distances like a sensor attached to the robot, it is recommended using a Laser Imaging Detection and Ranging (LiDAR) Camera. An example of this could be the **Intel RealSense L515 LiDAR Camera**² due to its reliability and precision.

3.3. SDN / NFV Network Infrastructure

The AI-PRISM network infrastructure layer will enable interoperable communication among sensors, the AI-PRISM Data Platform, edge devices, and AI-PRISM software components. This layer has the challenge of guaranteeing Quality of Service (QoS) and flexibility simultaneously in order to provide a robust but flexible communication infrastructure. For this, the key enablers are robust industrial IoT-based technologies as a flexible wireless sensing layer and the integration of software-defined

² <https://www.intelrealsense.com/lidar-camera-l515/>

networks in the industry. In this version of the document, the network infrastructure is based on a SDN paradigm [9].

The idea behind SDN is to create a centralized entity that has a global view of the network, even over multiple network technologies (e.g. Time Sensitive Networks (TSN), Ethernet, Wi-Fi, or IEEE 802.15.4 networks). The global knowledge obtained in this entity allows for optimizing decisions that guarantee the end-to-end quality of service.

This centralized entity is the SDN controller, which can manage multiple network technologies using their respective southbound protocol, and allows configuring the low-level behaviour of each device. This simplifies the development of applications and services in the fog because the SDN controller offers high-level APIs that connect applications with multiple network technologies without the need for them to know how to perform the low-level configuration. The foreseen advantages of this infrastructure can be summarized as follows:

- Centralization of network management
- Routing and network optimization
- Network monitoring and adaptation to changes
- Scheduled usage of the wireless medium
- On-demand resource request and allocation
- Isolation and prioritization of traffic flows
- End-to-end QoS management

3.3.1. Baseline Technical Specifications

From a technical level, the main objective is to implement a network architecture that enables robust, real-time, and secure integration between all AI-PRISM components, but with the challenge of providing QoS, flexibility, mobility, and scalability. Also integrate a Software Defined Wireless Sensor Network [10], which is a highly deterministic system that guarantees industrial-level requirements using wireless communication technologies developed by ITI, the leader of the development of the SDN/NFV Network Infrastructure. As highlighted in Figure 5, this infrastructure is the main enabler to achieving real-time communications in AI-PRISM. It has a stack of protocols that allow centralized control of all processes in the nodes (e.g. Medium Access Control - MAC, Routing, QoS, Application). This as mentioned above is based on the SDN paradigm, which manages networks by separating the control plane and the data plane. The control plane is entirely software-controlled, where a centralized agent, in this case, an SDN controller, makes decisions to configure resources and rules in the nodes. The data or forwarding plane are made up of the nodes, which operate in plug-and-play mode, as the controller sends each node all the necessary instructions to achieve maximum performance. In addition, the SDN controller is used as an integration point for the physical network

infrastructure and the application that collects the network information and requests network reconfiguration. For that, use a specific protocol for each network technology, for example, OpenFlow for wired SDN network, NetFlow for TSN, and even non-standard protocols such as SDN WISE for WSN.

Figure 5: AI-PRISM Real Time Communications Network

On the bottom layer, this component will focus on the communication technologies to develop, integrate, and provide a real-time communications infrastructure, both wired and wireless, as the basis for supporting the convergence of Information Technology (IT) and Operational Technology (OT) traffic. This architecture will enable robust, real-time, and secure communications in the distributed AI-PRISM system, but with the challenge of providing the needed flexibility, mobility, and scalability for the proposed scenarios. Robust technologies based on IIoT, a flexible wireless sensing layer, and the integration of software-defined networks in the industry will be the main drivers.

On the top layer, the SDN Controller will provide support for messaging protocols such as MQTT, or KAFKA, and a management API so that the AI-PRISM Data Platform can define and develop all the communication functionality required. The AI-PRISM Data Platform will also provide unified models (i.e. AI-PRISM Data Model) and APIs offering access to data resources (e.g. topics of the data broker and records of repositories), data management functions (filtering, normalization, missing data), and device management functions on top of this communication infrastructure. ARTEMIS³ is the

³ <https://www.wings-ict-solutions.eu/artemis/>

candidate solution identified to implement these functions, which will be further elaborated in **section 5.1.2** in future releases of this document.

3.4. Fog Cluster

As indicated above, the concept of using remote infrastructure to perform the computations of IoT data is called cloud computing and it is widely used to perform integration and sharing of data and resources between different systems to optimize the effectiveness of utilization of these shared systems.

Although cloud computing provides special services for WSN which allow remote sensing and monitoring over the Internet, the cloud performance is constrained by the time it takes to share the data between devices, as it can be inferred from the following simple equation:

$$\text{Latency} = \text{Time from device to cloud} + \text{Time data analysis} + \text{Time from cloud to device}$$

This yields that long delays in device-cloud communications can render real-time requirements hard or even impossible to meet.

The idea behind using a Fog Computing Cluster or Fog Cluster for short, is to make an extension of the cloud, in order to effectively reduce the latency by placing the services for data processing nearer to the objects that generate IoT information data [8]. The concept of fog computing will not eliminate the cloud technology, but instead, it should be considered as an extension of it since it has its same roles.

This way, this Fog Cluster can be considered as the hardware infrastructure supporting the deployment of the AI-PRISM IIoT Platform: A highly virtualized platform that performs computation, storage, as well as networking services between the network edge devices and the cloud tier. It will communicate all the devices within a physical space, and may act as a central node for expensive computations that require a fast response. It can also act as a translator node that will treat and filter data coming from the edge devices in order to send to the cloud more relevant data for it to be computed or stored. The AI-PRISM IIoT Platform is based on Kubernetes⁴, and is described in **section 4.2**.

As stated before, the Fog Cluster acts as a mid-point between the Cloud and the end devices. Since the bottleneck of this design dwells around the connectivity between the cloud and the Fog cluster, as well as our ability to treat the data gathered by the end devices, it is imperative to process data at the lowest possible level. For example, if a particular system relies on knowing the position of a particular object calculated from the data of the 3D point cloud acquiring unit, it would be wise (if possible) to compute this position at the acquiring unit itself. Doing so reduces the data flow between

⁴ <https://kubernetes.io/en/>

devices and reduces the computational stress on the upper units. In other words, we should try to avoid as much as possible communication with the cloud, by pre-treating the data at lower levels.

3.4.1. Baseline Technical Specifications

The software modules that will be deployed in the fog cluster require graphic acceleration (use of graphics processing units to enhance the computational capabilities in the fog cluster). As an example of computing devices with graphic acceleration that could be used in the fog cluster are the NVIDIA **Jetson Nano**⁵ and the **Jetson Orin**⁶ embedded boards.

The Jetson Nano embedded board can be installed on-board the end devices. It has a decent processing power and graphical acceleration⁷. It also supports the installation of the runtime environments considered and described in the next sections. Additionally, it offers several options regarding Input / Output (I/O) ports to use and therefore can be used to control a wide variety of hardware components.

Similarly, the Jetson Orin board can be used as a central node to provide additional computational resources in the fog tier. The Jetson Orin is the most powerful commercial Board in matter of processing power and also allows for graphical acceleration. This board also provides compatibility with Kubernetes containers and excels at network communication speed. The main idea is that the Jetson Orin board acts like a central coordination unit in each workstation, commanding each Jetson Nano board which would act like a kind of intermediary between the central coordination unit and each end device.

3.5. Cloud Cluster

The Cloud Cluster is as described above, the infrastructure used for cloud computing consisting of a set of machines hosted in the cloud for running the services that are not sensitive to latency, or that need to be placed in the cloud to enable effective communications between remote connections. These services are identified in the reference architecture as the AI-PRISM Continuous Integration and Continuous Deployment (CI/CD) services, which are the services that allow streamlining the deployment of AI-PRISM ambient, and the AI-PRISM Collaboration Network Services that enable remote access to open pilots.

3.5.1. Baseline Technical Specifications

The cloud cluster is not a key technical result of AI-PRISM, but rather, the additional infrastructure necessary to enable key collaborative features of AI-PRISM. As such, partners involved in the development and provisioning of the software components hosted in the cloud can select the most

⁵ <https://developer.nvidia.com/embedded/jetson-nano-developer-kit>

⁶ <https://www.nvidia.com/en-us/autonomous-machines/embedded-systems/jetson-orin/>

⁷ <https://developer.nvidia.com/embedded/jetson-benchmarks>

suitable alternative to optimize resources (e.g. machines in a data centre, a virtual data centre, a managed containerization cluster, managed services, or a combination of these options).

4. Runtime Environments

4.1. AI-PRISM ROS Framework

ROS (Robot Operating System) is an open-source software meant to help build robot applications, ranging from drivers to state-of-the-art algorithms, and including powerful developer tools. Currently, it is not only used in the field of robotics, but also in a wide range of sectors and applications due to its simplicity of use and its excellence in matter of communication between applications and systems.

As depicted in the Reference Architecture Overview section, the AI-PRISM ROS Framework will be deployed in the robot devices in the device tier, but it is necessary to consider at this stage interactions with other robotic applications for two reasons. First, ROS might not be compatible with e.g. real-time requirements on specific use cases, so it is wise to keep the reference architecture open to non-ROS architectures until the use case requirements are fully defined. Second, AI-PRISM needs to be able to integrate with robots that are already installed in the collaboration workspace, and in any case implement mechanism to integrate with as many robot architectures as possible to increase the potential impact of the technical results.

Regarding real time communications, other non-ROS architectures can be found, such as OROCOS which excels in its real-time control, OpenRDK, OpenRTM or YARP which was intended for humanoid robotics. Nonetheless, ROS not only provides us with a standardised base for robot application development but is also supported by an extensive and growing community making it the currently preferred tool by developers and industries. In parallel with ROS, we can find other initiatives such as ROS2 or ROS Industrial which solve and improve the ROS lacking capabilities, such as real-time control, and impulse its integration in the industry. As for navigation ROS provides off-the-self, ready-to-use capabilities like Simultaneous Localization and Mapping (SLAM) and Adaptive Monte Carlo Localization (AMCL) and is compatible with a high number of open source modules, as well as tools for debugging, visualisation, and simulation. For these reasons, ROS is identified in the DOA and in this deliverable as the primary robotic framework. The next sections include some important details of the ROS architecture and ROS version to be used.

4.1.1. ROS Architecture

The ROS 2 has distributed real-time system architecture. Sensors in robots, motion controllers, detection algorithms, artificial intelligence algorithms, navigation algorithms, etc. are all components (called nodes) of this distributed architecture.

The DDS (Data Distribution Service) middleware selected with ROS 2 for data exchange enables these components to communicate with each other in a distributed environment.

Distributed applications are designed as units known as nodes. All nodes in the system can be run on a single computer or they can be distributed and run across multiple computers.

Nodes communicate with each other via Topics, Services and Actions.

The **topic**-based communication uses a publish-subscribe architecture⁸ where the data produced and published by a node is subscribed by one or more node.

Service calls use a remote request-response approach from an application to another.

Actions are an approach used for long service calls, where a node not only makes a request and waits for a response, but can also receive a status via intermediate results.

4.1.2. ROS Version

ROS1 was designed with a couple of characteristics in mind: It was intended to control a single robot, no real time requirements where needed, an excellent connectivity between nodes even using different network types, etc.

ROS 1 fulfilled these requirements very well and it became much more robust than the designers initially intended. However, it still has some limitations which ROS2 tries to address.

Stated this, ROS2 was implemented to fulfil the following: Standardize an environment to work with Multi-Robot Systems, control and communication using Embedded Systems (Raspberry Pi, Arduino, etc.), facilitate the creation of patterns and templates for building and structuring systems while keeping flexibility, use safer communication protocols to avoid any potential risk of data leakages, etc.

ROS1, added a lot of Open Source unique libraries which have proven to be particularly useful when programming robots and configuration applications. In the early stages of ROS2, a lot of this libraries did not have ROS2 compatibility. This resulted into having to run our environments with both, ROS1 and ROS2 frameworks, and using bridges to communicate with both, resulting into losing some of those interesting features that could only be used when running singularly. The current reality is that every day, more and more of these useful open-source libraries are, not only porting their libraries to ROS2, but also stop updating them for ROS1. In fact, it should be emphasized that support for ROS ends on May the 1st of 2025, before the end date of the AI-PRISM project.

Stated this, it is imperative to use ROS2, since using ROS1 would translate into a degenerative obsolescence.

⁸ http://wiki.ros.org/ROS/Concepts#ROS_Computation_Graph_Level

ROS2 also includes the following features: Zeroconf, Protocol Buffers, Zero Message Queues (MQ) (and other message queues), Redis, Web Sockets, monitorisation of ROS2 applications, multi-platform compatibility between Linux, MacOS and Windows systems, and Data Distribution Service (DDS).

This DDS is a publish-subscribe transport model that replaces the communication method used in ROS1. The way it works is similar to the ROS1 services, which make a request to send a message and wait for a response. This method which allows the communication between two nodes without the need for a centralized program (like the ROS1 Master), making the communication more robust and flexible.

Another interesting feature is the fact that even ROS1 can be deployed in all, Linux, MacOS and Windows, only ROS2, allows multi-platform communication, between different systems.

More particularly, we are going to use ROS2 Humble, since the rest of ROS2 versions are about to lose their support.

4.2. [AI-PRISM IIoT Platform](#)

As described above, ROS provides the runtime environment for the different modules that will be deployed in the device tier. In a similar way, the AI-PRISM IIoT Platform provides a runtime for the services to be deployed in the Fog Cluster. The IIoT Platform integrates a set of components that collectively allow system administrators to browse, select, deploy, monitor, update, and scale AI-PRISM services running in the fog cluster. The AI-PRISM IIoT Platform is in this version as stated before based on Kubernetes, which is an open-source system for automating deployment, scaling, and management of containerized applications, and is becoming the de-facto operating system for cloud-based applications. In the Kubernetes architecture, containerized application run on nodes, which are either virtual or physical machines conforming the cluster. The services of the control plane are handled by the master node(s) and the main functionality is described as follows:

- **API Server:** Provides an internal and external programming interface to manage containerized applications across worker (non-master) nodes (workloads, networks, resources), exposing scheduling and controller functions.
- **Scheduler:** Monitors resources used on each node and balances workloads based on the constraints (resource requirements, resource availability, or other constraints) defined for the deployment of applications.
- **Controller:** Ensures that the actual cluster state is in accordance with the desired state.

Figure 6 IIoT Platform inner architecture

From this perspective, the services, and modules deployable in the Fog Cluster (either reasoning modules, perception modules, Simulation modules, collaboration modules, or AI-PRISM Data Platform services) are Kubernetes applications, packaged in a distributable format and available in an application registry in the AI-PRISM CI/CD Framework. The cluster management service gathers additional Kubernetes cluster management services to facilitate the administration of the cluster, allowing administrator users to browse the application registry, select one application, and install it. It also gathers services to monitor the status of installed applications. In this sense, the open-source Rancher⁹ provides services and management user interfaces to download and install Kubernetes applications from remote catalogues, and to monitor the health and status of the cluster. Lens¹⁰ is another open-source Kubernetes management software providing advanced status monitoring and control dashboards to manage Kubernetes clusters.

As mentioned above, it is envisioned that the reasoning, perception, and simulation modules require graphic acceleration. This requirement has been already factored in the specifications of the fog cluster hardware, and consequently, the Kubernetes configuration needs to provide support for graphic acceleration in worker nodes.

4.2.1. Workload placement

Based on the definitions provided, there are different options available to balance the workloads of the different AI-PRISM software modules. The leader of each solution should decide which workloads will be placed in the device tier, running in the native AI-PRISM ROS Framework, and which workloads will be placed in the fog tier, managed as Kubernetes applications. In this sense, it is important to note that ROS2 can also be containerized, deployed, and managed as Kubernetes,

⁹ <https://www.rancher.com/>

¹⁰ <https://k8slens.dev/>

so that the leader of each AI-PRISM software modules can decide which parts of the Kubernetes application run in the ROS2 network and which ones run in a different network. At this reporting period (M3), this design consideration is still open and the reference architecture is defined to be flexible enough to accommodate different design alternatives.

5. Software Components

5.1.1. AI-PRISM CI/CD Framework (CD) (PIAP)

Continuous Integration (CI) is a widely established development practice in the software development industry, in which members of a team integrate and merge development work (e.g., code) frequently, for example multiple times per day. CI enables software companies to have frequent releases (shorter release cycles), improve software quality, and increase their teams' productivity. This practice includes automated software building and testing.

Without loss of generality, let us consider an application that has its code stored in a Git¹¹ repository in GitLab¹². Developers push code changes very often, sometimes multiple times a day. For every push to the repository, a set of scripts could be created to build and test an application automatically, decreasing the chance of introducing errors to the application. This practice is known as Continuous Integration; for every change submitted to an application - even to development branches – it is built and tested automatically and continuously, ensuring the introduced changes pass all tests, guidelines, and code compliance standards which are established for the application. GitLab and GitHub¹³ are examples of collaborative development platforms providing services for Continuous Integration as a software development method. For every push to the project, devOps engineers (the team members in charge of CI/CD) can develop and configure a set of scripts the code is checked against.

Continuous Deployment (CD) practice goes a step further and automatically and continuously deploys the application to production or customer environments. There is a robust debate in academic and industrial circles about defining and distinguishing between continuous deployment and continuous delivery. What differentiates continuous deployment from continuous delivery is a production environment (i.e. actual customers): the goal of continuous deployment practice is to automatically and steadily deploy every change into the production environment. It is important to note that CD practice implies CDE (Continuous delivery) practice but the converse is not true. Whilst the final deployment in CDE is a manual step, there should be no manual steps in CD, in which as soon as developers commit a change, the change is deployed to production through a deployment pipeline. CDE practice is a pull-based approach for which a business decides what and when to

¹¹ <https://git-scm.com/>

¹² <https://about.gitlab.com/>

¹³ <https://github.com/>

deploy; CD practice is a push-based approach. In other words, the scope of CDE does not include frequent and automated release, and CD is consequently a continuation of CDE. Whilst CDE practice can be applied for all types of systems and organizations, CD practice may only be suitable for certain types of organizations or systems.

Another recent methodology, named Machine Learning Operations (MLOps¹⁴) extends the concepts of CI/CD to support the lifecycle management of machine learning models, considering also data preparation and model training as differentiated stages in the lifecycle of the application building process. MLOps platforms such as MLFlow¹⁵ integrate with git-based platforms and provide enhanced support to the development of machine learning models.

¹⁴ <https://ml-ops.org>

¹⁵ <https://mlflow.org/>

5.1.1.1 Internal Functions

Figure 7 AI-PRISM CI/CD Service internal functions

Figure 7 depicts the internal functions of the AI-PRISM CI/CD Services and the relationship to the AI-PRISM IIoT Platform internal architecture and functions described above in **section 4.2**. Developers release new versions of software in a code repository (Git repository). This software release triggers the execution of a CI/CD pipeline in a CI/CD worker (a cloud computing resource dedicated to run the build, integration, and test scripts specified in the pipelines). If the pipeline successfully runs all the tests, a new version of the application is published in the Application repository. The cluster control function of the AI-PRISM IIoT Platform fetches the versions available in the repository and notifies the administration user that there is a new version available, so that, in the end, the system administration is responsible of confirming the update process.

During the execution of the CI/CD Pipeline, the CI/CD workers use services of the AI-PRISM CI/CD to perform a software quality analysis (a static code analysis using open solutions like SonarQube¹⁶) as well as tests in an integrated test environment (a cloud replica of a production environment) to

¹⁶ <https://www.sonarqube.org>

detect possible integration issues. Figure 8 provides a more detailed description of the CI/CD workflow.

Figure 8: AI-PRISM CI workflow

The workflow is shown in Figure 9. New feature is created, then developed and committed to the repository. Then, the code is automatically built and unit tests, integration tests, etc. are performed. If at any stage it fails, fixes should be implemented and the procedure should be started again. Continuous deployment is the process of moving software that has been built and tested successfully into production which is shown in the Figure 10.

Figure 11: AI-PRISM CD workflow

New features are developed. Then building is done, unit tests are performed. After performing static code analysis and integration tests, the result is published to artifactory. Then comes the testing phase. Changes must pass user acceptance and performance tests. Only after these stages can the result go into production environment.

5.1.1.2 Candidate Solutions

Solution	Description
Gitlab	GitLab is an open-source end-to-end software development platform with built-in version control, issue tracking, code review, CI/CD, and more. GitLab can be self-hosted on any server, in a container, or on a cloud provider.
GitHub	GitHub is a code hosting platform for version control and collaboration. It has similar features to GitLab, but it is not open source.
SonarQube	SonarQube is a tool for continuous static code analysis in terms of quality. It enables the automatic detection of errors, and weak points causing a decrease in security and the so-called “code smells”. It can find fragments that have been duplicated, which allows to reduce the amount of code. The main benefits of using SonarQube are the improvement of the quality and security of the created code as well as the control and reduction of technological debt.
MLFlow	MLflow is a platform to streamline machine learning development, including tracking experiments, packaging code into reproducible runs, and sharing and deploying models. MLflow offers a set of lightweight APIs that can be used with any existing machine learning application or library (TensorFlow, PyTorch, XGBoost, etc), wherever you currently run ML code (e.g. in notebooks, standalone applications or the cloud).

Figure 12 Candidate solutions integrating the AI-PRISM CI/CD Services

5.1.1.3 Inputs

As described in the previous section, the main Input of the AI-PRISM CI/CD Services is the software updates provided by developers. This interface should use the git protocol interfaces and message formats so that it can be integrated with any development environment.

5.1.1.4 Outputs

The main outputs of the component are the reports of the test results delivered to developers, and the applications released in the application repository. The preferred format for the test results is a graphic report highlighting the main software quality issues and listing the unitary tests that were not passed. The preferred format for the application repository is a release code repository which can be accessed from the IIoT Platform using the git protocol interfaces and message formats. The preferred format for the application is a packaged Kubernetes application format like Helm¹⁷ charts.

¹⁷ <https://helm.sh/es/docs/topics/charts/>

5.1.1.5 Interfaces

The interfaces of the AI-PRISM CI/CD Services are the user interfaces provided to developers to manage software updates and visualize the status of pipelines and test results, and the git interfaces to integrate with IDEs and cluster management control.

Figure 13 Screenshot of CI/CD Pipelines in Gitlab

5.1.1.6 Related components

All software components use this component in design time to support the development lifecycle. The AI-PRISM IIoT Platform uses the git interface to access the application repository.

5.1.2. AI-PRISM Data Platform (DS)

The detailed definition of this component is not documented in this reporting period (M3). The first version will be provided at M6 and the final version at M12.

5.1.3. AI-PRISM Communication Modules (CM)

The detailed definition of this component is not documented in this reporting period (M3). The first version will be provided at M6 and the final version at M12.

5.1.4. AI-PRISM Simulation Environment (SE)

The detailed definition of this component is not documented in this reporting period (M3). The first version will be provided at M6 and the final version at M12.

5.1.4.1 *Related Components*

5.1.5. AI-PRISM Ambient Digitalisation Modules (AD)

The detailed definition of this component is not documented in this reporting period (M3). The first version will be provided at M6 and the final version at M12.

5.1.6. AI-PRISM AI-based Perception Enhancing Modules (PE)

The detailed definition of this component is not documented in this reporting period (M3). The first version will be provided at M6 and the final version at M12.

5.1.7. AI-PRISM Agent Level Reasoning Modules (DR)

The detailed definition of this component is not documented in this reporting period (M3). The first version will be provided at M6 and the final version at M12.

5.1.8. AI-PRISM AI-based Ambient Level Reasoning Modules (DR)

The detailed definition of this component is not documented in this reporting period (M3). The first version will be provided at M6 and the final version at M12.

5.1.9. AI-PRISM Human – Machine Interaction (HMI) modules (HI)

The detailed definition of this component is not documented in this reporting period (M3). The first version will be provided at M6 and the final version at M12.

5.1.10. AI-PRISM Programming by Demonstration (PD)

The detailed definition of this component is not documented in this reporting period (M3). The first version will be provided at M6 and the final version at M12.

5.1.11. AI-PRISM Human Safety Management Procedures (SP)

The detailed definition of this component is not documented in this reporting period (M3). The first version will be provided at M6 and the final version at M12.

6. Implementation Guidelines

6.1. Implementation Calendar

The DOA provides a description of the planning of design (WP2), implementation (WP3-WP5), and demonstration and validation activities in AI-PRISM. As stated in the DOA, the project will follow a hybrid agile-waterfall approach for software development. A complete release of the Reference Framework and Specification will be released in M6 to kick-off development activities, which start in M7 and are organized in periodic releases or sprints. The design of the Reference Architecture is not finalized until M12. This overlap between the architecture design exercise and the development activities allows to feed back to the reference architecture the results and the knowledge gained from actual development, aligned with the agile principle of delivering early and continuously.

The demonstration and validation activities are also executed in parallel. Linked to the industrial scenarios and requirements analysis (WP1), the process starts with the collection of requirements in pilot use cases, which runs in parallel and feeds to the Reference Architecture and the definition of functional and technical specifications. Furthermore, AI-PRISM solutions are human-centric thanks to the integration of Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) from the identification of requirements for the design of new systems to the final stage of evaluation and validation. The project benefits from human analysis techniques that capture both quantitative measures as well as qualitative rich data across the different demonstrators (WP5), delivering an initial report (First Task Analysis for benchmarking and design requirements) in M6. Besides this, the integration of solutions in industrial environments (WP5) starts as early as in M12, so that training data can be collected on-site and solutions can further evolve based on user feedback in pilot scenarios. This planning is as mentioned reflected in the description of the action and summarized in the Gantt chart of the DOA included in Figure 14.

Figure 14 AI-PRISM Gantt chart (source DOA)

The objective of this section is to provide a general planning of activities to effectively implement the methodology envisioned in the DOA, organizing development activities into a calendar that is consistent with the overall project plan and methodologies. In particular, the development of AI-enhancing tools and the generation of realistic simulation environments requires the collection of

large amounts of training data, and this needs to be considered in the planning, and well aligned with the activities needed to commission the hardware to realise the pilot demonstrators.

The approach is to consider the following calendar phases for all activities:

1. **Initial definition phase (M1-M6):** This phase focuses on producing an initial set of requirements, specifications, and reference architecture design so that development activities can start as soon as possible. It frames the human analysis activities conducted in WP5 collecting data in situ on pilots to ensure human centred design.
2. **Early prototyping phase (M7-M12):** This phase conveys the first months of the development activities. The requirements and specifications are reviewed iteratively together with the end users, and mockups, early prototypes and proof of concepts are used to validate alternative design proposals. The solutions are not integrated in the industrial environments of the pilots, so it is not possible to collect training data on-site, or at least, it is not possible to collect training data using sensors or data infrastructure that are not already available in the industrial scenarios. In this phase, the focus is on co-design and validation with industrial owners, and on integrating the different AI-PRISM components together. Training data is collected in laboratory conditions.
3. **Integration phase (M13-M18):** This phase starts with the release of the first version of the AI-PRISM components that implements the interfaces defined in the reference architecture (Milestone 5) in M12. The focus is to integrate the components in the industrial pilots, and start the procurement and engineering of the hardware components, which for robotic components such as robotic arms or Autonomous Mobile Robots (AMRs) can span for several months. The procurement and integration of the sensors and edge and fog equipment required to build training data sets so that data can be collected in the industrial scenarios as early as possible.
4. **Commissioning phase (M19-M24):** In this phase, the commissioning of all the required equipment is completed. The end of this phase corresponds to Milestone 6. All the hardware is installed in the demonstration scenarios, and all the solutions are ready to be tested on-site, including the AI-PRISM Open Access Pilot.
5. **Improvement phase (M25-M36):** From M25 and until the end of the project, the improvement phase comprises the collection and preparation of data collected on-site to re-train the models, and the improvement of all solutions through experiments with end users at the pilot sites. It includes the major third release of all solutions (Milestone 7, M30), the final validation and demonstration, and the final release of the software (Milestone 8, M36).

Figure 15 represents this overall planning of activities.

Figure 15 Overall planning of activities

ANNEX A: References

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